

1 Highlights

2 **BIM-based semantic enrichment and knowledge graph generation via geometric relation** 3 **checking**

- 4 • Semantic connection inference among BIM elements, using geometric relation checking.
- 5 • Geometric Relation Checking (GRC) tool description.
- 6 • Cross-domain semantic integration of large fragmented BIM data sets.
- 7 • Detection of design errors among BIM elements.
- 8 • HVAC building topology generation supporting BIM2BEM workflows.

11 **Abstract**

12 Building Information Models support information exchange and collaboration between designers, engi-
13 neers and stakeholders of the built environment. Due to the large scale and multi-domain requirements
14 of building projects, building information is often fragmented to multiple files, prone to modelling errors
15 and poor level of detail. As a result, BIM data cannot be reused and remain siloed across the building
16 lifecycle. This paper introduces the Geometric Relation Checking tool, a novel tool that automatically
17 detects geometric relations between IFC objects. These relationships can be used to infer missing se-
18 mantic relationships among these objects, increasing the inter-connectivity among semantic graphs of
19 different domains and at the same time breaking their siloed structures. The tool is tested on MEP
20 and architecture domain data, but its use can be generalized to any other data domain that contains
21 elements with geometric representations.

22 *Keywords:* BIM, IFC, Geometry, Interoperability, Digital Twins, Semantic Web Technologies

23 **1. Introduction**

24 Building Information Modeling (BIM) has transformed the construction industry by creating a
25 collaborative and comprehensive data environment that supports building design, construction, and
26 operation. BIM models contain detailed information—including geometry, spatial relationships, and
27 semantic data—that enables the analysis and simulation of various aspects of the building, such as
28 structural behavior, energy performance, and construction sequencing. An open data format is essen-
29 tial to facilitate seamless data exchange among stakeholders who use different software applications.
30 Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) provide this interoperability as an open standard-based file format,
31 making it a cornerstone of the BIM process by enabling BIM data to be shared across diverse platforms.

32 Ensuring accurate and consistent geometric relationships between building elements, or the spatial
33 information that defines how pairs of elements relate (relative position, proximity, containment, ...), is
34 essential for effectively implementing BIM-based workflows in an IFC model. While tools for checking
35 geometric relationships exist to enhance the quality of IFC models (Solibri, TEKLA model checker, and
36 others), the potential to leverage these relationships using spatial reasoning for inferring non-geometric
37 semantics remains relatively unexplored. For example, spatial relationships between elements—such
38 as adjacency, containment, and intersection—can help infer non-geometric relationships. Adjacency
39 might indicate connectivity when one element is attached to another, while containment could imply
40 inheritance when one element is enclosed within another. Manually checking these relationships by
41 visual inspection is a time-consuming and error-prone task, particularly in large and complex models.
42 Therefore, automated geometry relation-checking processes are essential to help BIM users detect these
43 relationships and infer other non-geometric semantics.

44 The need for multi-domain collaborative information exchange and less rigid information exchange
45 structures appears to be driving increasing interest in the use of property and knowledge graphs [1].
46 Such approaches are increasingly useful in operations and management, where several ontologies have
47 been introduced and standards such as ASHRAE 223P [2] are emerging [3]. The understanding is that
48 in many such cases, detailed geometric information is not important, but rather topological relations

49 among elements suffice. Yet extracting such topological information remains a manual — and often
50 tedious — task that requires an understanding of the geometric relations between building elements
51 to infer topological information. Extracting the topological information is a straightforward task in an
52 ideal case where all relationships have been explicitly and correctly modeled. Yet, enforcing such strict
53 quality requirements on the BIM models can be tedious and unrealistic and has been shown in practice
54 to be hard to attain — even when the best intentions exist. The reality is that available models can
55 have modeling omissions or errors, which are compounded by imperfect information transfer between
56 authoring tools and, more broadly, issues related to information extraction and transfer. Being able
57 to use the geometric context from a BIM model, even when such a model is imperfect or incomplete,
58 to infer topological information, can be quite useful. Extracting such topological information can
59 be useful in several contexts: for example, in the architectural context to infer connectivity between
60 spaces, or in the Mechanical Electrical and Plumbing (MEP) context to establish fluid flows (air, water,
61 or refrigerant) through distribution networks. Regardless of the domain, addressing the challenge of
62 extracting topological information requires returning to the geometric space. The use of geometric
63 relations among elements can help uncover additional semantic relations, regardless of the domains,
64 provided that a sufficient geometric context exists in these domains.

65 Motivated by the above, we introduce a four-step process that involves: the operations of a novel
66 Geometric Relation Checking (GRC) tool at its core and the use of a dedicated Geometry Exporter [4],
67 for the extraction of the IFC geometric context and its transformation to a GRC-compatible input.

68 The primary objective of this paper is to introduce a methodology that uses the previous four-step
69 process, to extract topological information from geometric data and generate or enrich a knowledge
70 graph with this information. To demonstrate and evaluate the proposed methodology, we consider a
71 specific and challenging use case: extracting the Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC)
72 topology of a building in a knowledge graph form, for use in operations and maintenance (O&M) contexts
73 or energy performance simulations. For this purpose, we need to use the solid geometric representations
74 of Mechanical Electrical and Plumbing (MEP) components and building spaces, as input. We apply the
75 GRC process on these representations, to identify the geometric relationships among these components
76 and, based on these relationships, infer their connectivity patterns and the locations of the HVAC
77 terminal units, to instantiate the final HVAC topology knowledge graph.

78 Considering the above, the structure of the paper evolves as follows: first, the background section
79 provides a review on Geometric Relation Checking (GRC) concepts. The four-step process is detailed
80 in Section 2. Section 4 demonstrates the application of the introduced process to MEP fluid transfer
81 networks, followed by examples of this application in Section 5. The paper concludes with three final
82 sections: Section 6 discusses the capabilities of the process, Section 7 addresses its limitations and
83 potential future improvements, and Section 8 resumes the work.

84 **2. Background**

85 Geometric relationships between the geometric representations of solid BIM elements can be used to
86 infer relationships like adjacency, clash, or containment, and it is broadly used when working with BIM
87 and related applications. We call the generic ability to detect such relationships, Geometric Relation
88 Checking (GRC); the concept of GRC is quite general and can have broad and far-reaching applications.
89 Typical uses include (i) clash detection to ensure a BIM model meets threshold quality requirements, (ii)
90 compliance checking, (iii) or for semantic enrichment of BIM models and the generation of knowledge
91 graphs. We discuss each of these areas below to highlight potential uses of our novel GRC tool that
92 performs GRC operations. In this paper, we focus on the ability to infer topological relationships using
93 GRC, which can be quite useful in several contexts that have not been adequately explored in the
94 literature.

95 2.1. Computer-aided design

96 The concept of geometric relation checking (GRC) emerged in an early form within computer-aided
97 design (CAD). While the notion of a construction or building element was absent in initial CAD data,
98 geometric relations such as distances and constraints among object lines in two dimensions or object
99 faces in three dimensions were evaluated through a process called dimensioning [5]. Dimensioning in-
100 volves adding measurements — such as length, width, and height — to a design, which serve to verify
101 the accuracy of geometric relationships, including distances and angles relative to an axis. Constraints,
102 on the other hand, are rules defining relationships between elements in CAD, such as parallelism or
103 perpendicularity. These fundamental GRC functions helped ensure design accuracy and manufactura-
104 bility in early CAD. At a later stage, five specific types of geometric relations were introduced in 3D
105 architectural CAD data: adjacency, containment, intersection, separation, and connectivity [6].

106 2.2. Building information models

107 In transitioning from CAD to Building Information Modeling (BIM), the concept of a building
108 or construction element — often referred to as a BIM element in a broad sense — became more
109 explicit. In the BIM context, GRC is used to verify relationships among the geometric representations
110 of BIM elements. These checks play a crucial role in automated rule-checking mechanisms [7], facilitate
111 3D information retrieval by exploring model topology [8], and support object classification processes
112 [9, 10]. In this context, GRC can be performed using the solid representations of octrees [11]. Octrees
113 are geometric data structures used to approximate solid objects by recursively dividing 3D space into
114 eight smaller cubic regions, or octants until each reaches a defined minimum volume. Each node in
115 an octree contains eight child nodes. This structure enables GRC operations between pairs of objects
116 by executing these operations on their corresponding child nodes. Finally, the concept of geometric
117 relation checking among architectural BIM elements has been used for graph data model creation [12]
118 and dimension reduction using graph models for simulation purposes [13], [14].

119 2.3. Clash detection

120 The geometric relation, defined as clash, when two solid objects have a non-trivial intersection, has
121 been extensively used as a BIM quality-checking mechanism. Clash detection [15] is used to ensure
122 that elements from different domains do not intersect. For instance, it verifies that architectural el-
123 ements, such as walls and floors, do not collide with MEP elements, including mechanical, electrical,
124 and plumbing systems. Also, clash detection has been used to support cross-domain BIM coordination
125 problems [16, 17] and reduce costs that occur from design errors and potential construction errors [18].
126 Clashes were classified further as geometric relations in [19]. Clashes are significant as incorrect or
127 incomplete geometric representations intersecting in a general 4D-BIM setup can lead to design errors,
128 construction delays, increased costs, and health and safety issues [20].

129 2.4. Code compliance checking

130 Another area where the GRC can provide insights is the automatic code compliance checking [21].
131 Within this subject, certain checking rules can be interpreted as relations among the geometric repre-
132 sentations of BIM elements. For example, the geometric relationships between the solid representations
133 of BIM objects can be used as a BIM validation methodology in health and safety compliance checks
134 [22]. Geometric relations among triangulated objects have also been used in automatic code compliance
135 checking operations for fire safety [23]. The topological spatial relationships (adjacency, connectivity,
136 and inclusion) among BIM objects have also been investigated using fast comparison rules on min/max
137 point coordinates for code compliance checking in [24]. As far as the implementation of code compliance
138 rules is concerned, GRC is also utilized by various software tools like Solibri Model Checker [25] and
139 specialized geometry engines such as FORNAX [26] and processing languages such as BERA [27]. GRC
140 concepts have been utilized alongside Graph Neural Networks (GNN) to carry out BIM quality control

141 tasks [28]. Additionally, GRC concepts have been applied for geometric quality checks (GQC) and the
142 creation of GQC knowledge graphs to ensure code compliance in construction projects [29].

143 2.5. Knowledge graphs

144 The formation of knowledge graphs within the BIM context to perform data queries has received
145 considerable attention [12, 30]. Although the geometric context of BIM data can be described in a
146 knowledge graph form [31], queries in this context are quite challenging. To address this, an ontology
147 named "File Ontology for Geometric Formats", or FOG [32], has been created to connect files containing
148 BIM geometric data, like glTF and OBJ files, with non-geometric knowledge graphs. Also, ways to
149 interlink these different geometric files have been investigated with GEOM ontology [33]. Several
150 ontologies have been developed to describe the geometric representation of solid objects including the
151 ontology of geometric primitives [34], and the Ontology Managing Geometry [35]. Although the previous
152 attempts at developing geometry-related ontologies, focus on the different geometric representations and
153 their links, to this day, no ontology supports the GRC concepts.

154 As it is reported also in [36], [37], GRC concepts can be used to infer missing semantic links among
155 BIM objects belonging to different data domains and enrich respective knowledge graphs with these
156 links. These research efforts highlight the need to define geometric relations among BIM elements more
157 formally according to a domain-agnostic format and to detect and generate instances of these relations
158 by applying GRC operations to BIM element pairs. For example, the detected geometric relationships
159 among geometric representations of HVAC element pairs can be used to form knowledge graphs [38],
160 using the brick ontology [39]. These graphs capture the connectivity patterns of a building's HVAC
161 network. The work presented here attempts to support such application of GRC concepts towards an
162 HVAC topology generation in a knowledge graph format.

163 Furthermore, triggered by the potential applications of the GRC concepts, the need to store these
164 relations in graph form, and the fact that there is no GRC ontology, one of the objectives of this work
165 is to introduce such an ontology (see Section 3.5).

166 3. Methodology

167 Certain geometric relations among BIM elements' solid geometric representations can be used to
168 detect missing semantic relationships. These geometric relations may include adjacency, clash, and
169 containment relations. This section introduces a process for identifying these geometric relations using
170 a dedicated tool called Geometric Relation Checker (GRC tool).

171 3.1. Process outline

172 To detect missing semantic relations among BIM elements using geometric means a four-step process
173 is introduced - this process is outlined in the block diagram of Figure 1. Input to the proposed method-
174 ology is a BIM model that includes geometric information, as would be exported from any authoring
175 tool using the Design Transfer View Model-View Definition. To make the discussion more concrete, we
176 consider an IFC model without loss of generality as input. The output of the process is the topological
177 information, which can be exported in several formats. Such information can enrich the original IFC
178 model semantically, a case that has been studied extensively. Rather, we focus on defining a compact
179 representation using RDF and a lightweight ontology to define the detected geometric relationships.
180 This compact representation can support different use cases including the one seen in the case study
181 below. It should be mentioned that the serialization approach is less critical in extracting the topology
182 itself, but the lightweight ontology presented in Section 3.5 can be useful in practical implementations.

183 1. Initially, the geometric content of the IFC file is extracted using the Geometry Exporter.

- 184 2. The extracted geometric content (from step 1), together with a list of GUIDs of elements to be
 185 checked and the check types, are fed to the GRC importer, which produces the input XML file of
 186 the Geometric Relation Checking tool (GRC tool).
- 187 3. The input data is processed by the Geometric Relation Checking tool. The checks are performed
 188 and the results are reported in an output XML file.
- 189 4. Using the output of step 3, the Knowledge Graph Generator can generate a final knowledge graph.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the knowledge graph generation produced by BIM geometric relation checking process.

190 The output of the final step (step 4) of the previous process is a knowledge graph. This is achieved
 191 using the Knowledge Graph Generator component (see Figure 1), which functions as an ETL process
 192 that transforms the data from the output XML file (step 3) into a knowledge graph, following a specific
 193 ontology, such as the one introduced in subsection 3.5. Using additional reasoning, the Knowledge
 194 Graph Generator component can also generate a knowledge graph based on other ontologies, as well.

195 This knowledge graph contains the geometric relationships among all the checked pairs of elements.
 196 These relationships can be exploited in several ways. In this study, the detected geometric relations
 197 among the solid representations of building HVAC elements and building spaces will be used to infer the
 198 connectivity of these components, establish paths from source to sink elements and pinpoint the locations
 199 of HVAC terminal units within the building’s spatial topology—crucial information for building energy
 200 performance simulations.

201 3.2. Geometric Relation Checking tool

202 The GRC tool which supports the checking of geometric relations is described in more detail in this
 203 section.

204 3.2.1. Description of operation

205 GRC is a software tool that checks the presence of certain geometric relations in pairs of input
 206 geometric representations of BIM elements defined broadly as definition shapes based on the IfcPro-
 207 ductDefinitionShape specification. At the moment, three geometric relation checks are implemented
 208 and used in GRC: adjacency, clash, and containment. These relations are illustrated in Figure 2, using
 209 the cubic solid geometric representations of an element pair (A, B).

210 The above geometric relations are defined as follows:

211 *Adjacency*: An adjacency is detected between two elements if their solid geometric representations
 212 share one or more common boundary surfaces. Such a common boundary surface, shared by the two
 213 solid geometric representations of an element pair (A, B), is displayed in blue in part A of Figure 2.
 214 Appropriate threshold values are defined to detect adjacency, based on plane distance, as described in
 215

Figure 2: Types of geometric relations between the solid geometric representations of two elements: (A) Adjacency, (B) Clash and (C) Containment

216 subsection 3.4.

217

218 *Clash*: A clash between two elements occurs if their solid geometric representations intersect with-
 219 out one fully containing the other. An example of such a clash, involving the intersecting geometric
 220 representations of element pair (A, B), is shown in part B of Figure 2. In this example, the clash
 221 surfaces are highlighted in blue.

222

223 *Containment*: A containment is detected between two elements if the solid geometric representation of
 224 one element is contained entirely inside the solid geometric representation of the other. A containment
 225 example, between the solid geometric representations of the elements (A, B), is demonstrated in part
 226 C of Figure 2.

227 3.2.2. GRC tool I/O specification

228 In general, the GRC tool performs pairwise geometric checks (as illustrated in Figure 2), between
 229 elements belonging to either one element set $A = \{A1, A2, \dots\}$ or two element sets $A = \{A1, A2, \dots\}$ and
 230 $B = \{B1, B2, \dots\}$. As illustrated in Figure 3, in both input and output data structures of GRC, a finite
 231 number of checks are defined along with units of length and area measurement. The checks in the input
 232 are mapped to the checks in the output in a one-to-one fashion: the first input check (that contains
 233 the check types, check relations and the sets A, or set A of elements to be checked), is mapped to the
 234 first check of the output (that contains the results of the check operations: the detected check relations
 235 and their respective check relation surfaces), and so on. Both input and output data files of GRC tool
 236 are illustrated for a clash detection check, in parts A and B of Figure 3, respectively. GRC has two
 237 additional output file exporting options: OBJ files for viewing purposes and BCF files to facilitate BIM
 238 collaboration. Next, we present GRC's input and output data structures.

239 GRC input

240 As mentioned above, the GRC input (illustrated in part A of Figure 3.) contains multiple check classes,
 241 each comprising subclasses that define the geometric representations of the objects to be examined.
 242 These objects are grouped into element sets (A and B) and are associated with specific types of checks
 243 to be performed. These subclasses are:

244

245 *CheckType*: Defines the type of the check that is going to be performed. It can attain one out of
 246 two possible string values: "CrossCheck" or "SelfCheck". If the CheckType has a "CrossCheck" value
 247 cross-checks among all elements of two sets A and B are going to be performed. If the CheckType has a
 248 "SelfCheck" value, checks among all possible pairs of elements belonging to a single set A, are going to
 249 be performed. In the last case, all commutative pairs will be checked once (checks (A_i, A_j) and (A_j, A_i))

250 are the same, where $A_i, A_j \in A$).

251

252 *CheckRelations*: Contains one or more CheckRelation subclasses. Each CheckRelation contains the
253 geometric relationship type to be checked, as a string attribute and additional parameters (if any) as
254 additional attributes. Currently, three CheckRelation types are supported that are defined as the fol-
255 lowing string attributes: "Adjacency", "Clash" and "Containment".

256

257 *ElementSetA*: Contains information about the objects that belong to set A.

258

259 *ElementSetB*: Contains information about the objects that belong to set B. It exists only if the Check-
260 Type has the "CrossCheck" value.

261

262 The elements listed in the element sets A and B represent structured data points that refer to the
263 properties of an object in a Building Information Modeling (BIM) environment, specifically using IFC
264 (Industry Foundation Classes) standards. Each element contains data relevant to the 3D spatial config-
265 uration and geometric description of the respective BIM object, contained in the following data classes:

266

267 *GID*: Contains a unique, 25-character identifier called an IFC GUID (Globally Unique Identifier) as a
268 string. It ensures each object being checked has a distinct ID, which is essential for referencing specific
269 objects in the IFC model.

270

271 *GlbLocations*: Includes the location vectors of the object's placement transformations in 3D, listed
272 as successive IfcLocalPlacement transformations. It is formatted as a string in the form:

273

274 "[l_{1x}, l_{1y}, l_{1z}], [l_{2x}, l_{2y}, l_{2z}], ...]", where each " l_x, l_y, l_z " defines the coordinates of each transformation's
275 origin point, which affects the object's position in 3D space.

276

277 *GlbAxes*: Stores the axis vectors for each placement transformation, also following successive IfcLo-
278 calPlacement transformations in 3D. The vectors are given as: "[a_{1x}, a_{1y}, a_{1z}], [a_{2x}, a_{2y}, a_{2z}], ...]", repre-
279 senting the direction of each axis. Each vector has a Euclidean norm of 1, meaning it is a unit vector,
280 ensuring standard length and orientation consistency across transformations.

281

282 *GlbDirections*: Defines the direction vectors of each transformation in 3D, formatted similarly to axis
283 vectors, with each direction vector " dx, dy, dz " also having a unit length (norm of 1). This stan-
284 dardization guarantees consistent orientation and rotation for each transformation in the object's local
285 coordinate system.

286

287 *DefinitionShape*: One or more DefinitionShape classes describe the object's geometric form, including
288 parametric (dimension-based) and non-parametric shapes. Each shape follows the IfcProductDefini-
289 tionShape format from IFC4 standards, providing a comprehensive geometric description for quality
290 control. GRC (Geometric Relation Checking) tools support various DefinitionShapes, which represent
291 different geometric representations needed for diverse BIM applications.

292 Together, these data classes form a structured way to represent and validate an object's 3D placement,
293 orientation, and shape in IFC-based BIM models, which is essential for automated checking and quality
294 control.

295 *GRC output*

296 As mentioned above, the GRC output (illustrated in part B of Figure 3.) contains multiple check
297 classes, each comprising of subclasses that contains the results of the checks defined in the input. These
298 subclasses are:

299

300 *CheckRelation*: This class can be either: Clash, Containment, or Adjacency, depending on the de-
301 tected geometric relation for the respective check. In the example of part B of Figure 3 a Clash is
302 presented as a detected CheckRelation element. Each CheckRelation element contains the following
303 string attributes:

304

- The check ID number as Check_ID,

305

- The internal element ID number of the first element involved in the detected CheckRelation from
306 the set A, as ElementA_ID1.

307

- The IFC GUID of the first element involved in the detected Check relation from set A, as Ele-
308 mentA_GID1.

309

- The internal element id number of the second element involved in the detected CheckRelation,
310 which is defined either: in set A as ElementA_ID2 if the CheckType of the Check is defined as a
311 "SelfCheck" in the input, or in set B as ElementB_ID2 if the CheckType of the Check is defined
312 as a "CrossCheck" in the input.

313

- The IFC GUID of the second element, involved in the detected CheckRelation, which is taken
314 either from set A as ElementA_GID2 if the CheckType of the Check is defined as a "SelfCheck" in
315 the input, or set B as ElementB_GID2 if the CheckType of the Check is defined as a "CrossCheck"
316 in the input.

317 Each CheckRelation subclass contains a CheckRelationSurfaces subclass that contains the surfaces if
318 any, of the CheckRelation, as described next.

319

320 *CheckRelationSurfaces*: Depending on the type of the detected CheckedRelation, the CheckRelation-
321 Surfaces can be one of the following: ClashSurfaces, AdjacencySurfaces, or ContainmentSurfaces. In the
322 example presented in part B of Figure 3, since the detected CheckRelation is a Clash the CheckRelation
323 surfaces are defined as ClashSurfaces. Each of the detected CheckRelation surfaces are planar poly-
324 gons, they are defined using one outerContour element, describing the outer perimeter of the respective
325 polygon in 3D, and possible multiple innerContour elements describing its holes in 3D, if any. Each
326 of the outer- and inner-contour elements contains a set of points in 3D as elements point3D. Finally,
327 each of the point3D elements contains the coordinates of the respective point in 3D as x,y, and z string
328 attributes.

329 To give an example of the previous I/O specification, if the check type is a "CrossCheck", the check
330 relation is "Clash" $A = \{A1, A2, A3\}$ and $B = \{B1, B2\}$ the following $3 \times 2 = 6$ pairs of elements will
331 be checked for potential clashes:

332 $\{(A1, B1), (A1, B2), (A2, B1), (A2, B2), (A3, B1), (A3, B2)\}$. Alternatively, if in the previous input con-
333 figuration, the check type is "SelfCheck" without the element set B, then the pairs that will be checked
334 for potential clashes will be:

335 $\{(A1, A2), (A1, A3), (A2, A3)\}$.

A. GRC input

```
<g:GRC>
  <Units>
    <LengthUnit>METRE</LengthUnit>
  </Units>
  <Checks>
    <Check>
      <CheckType>CrossCheck</CheckType>
      <CheckRelations>
        <CheckRelation type="g:Adjacency"/>
        <CheckRelation type="g:Clash"/>
      </CheckRelations>
      <ElementSetA>
        <Element>
          <GID>3nGy4yKPP79u43sAb1qwiR</GID>
          <GlbLocations>[ [10.71, 13.86, 31.20], ... ]</GlbLocations>
          <GlbAxes>[ [0.0, 0.0, 1.0], ... ]</GlbAxes>
          <GlbDirections>[ [1.0, 0.0, 0.0], ... ]</GlbDirections>
          <DefinitionShape xsi:type="c:Manifold">
            ...
          </DefinitionShape>
        </Element>
      </ElementSetA>
      <ElementSetB>
        <Element>
          <GID>3YgrF9ZXXAixmPsWoGAXwp</GID>
          <DefinitionShape xsi:type="c:ExtrudedAreaSolid">
            ...
          </DefinitionShape>
        </Element>
      </ElementSetB>
    </Check>
  </Checks>
</g:GRC>
```

B. GRC output

```
<CheckReport>
  <Units>
    <LengthUnit>METRE</LengthUnit>
    <AreaUnit>SQUAREMETRE</AreaUnit>
  </Units>
  <Checks>
    <Check>
      <Clash Check_ID=1
        Clash_ID=1
        ElementA_ID1="1"
        ElementA_GID1="3nGy4yKPP79u43sAb1qwiR"
        ElementB_ID2="1"
        ElementB_GID2="3YgrF9ZXXAixmPsWoGAXwp"/>
      <ClashSurfaces>
        <surface>
          <outerContour>
            <point3D ID="1" x="..." y="..." z="...">
              ...
            </outerContour>
            <innerContours>
              <innerContour>
                <point3D ID="1" x="..." y="..." z="...">
                  ...
                </innerContour>
              </innerContours>
            </surface>
          </ClashSurfaces>
        </Clash>
      </Check>
    </Checks>
  </CheckReport>
```


Figure 3: Input and output XML file snippets of GRC tool.

336 3.3. GRC implementation and performance

337 At the current stage, GRC receives as input the solid geometric representations of BIM elements
338 that are defined according to the IfcProductDefinitionShape class. The GRC process consists of three
339 primary steps, executed sequentially by different subroutines. These steps include two input/output
340 interface steps (1 and 3) and a single core step (2):

- 341 1. Boundary Surface Extraction: In the first step, boundary representations of the elements to be
342 checked are extracted from the parsed input XML file. This involves converting the parametric
343 and non-parametric geometric descriptions of the elements' solids (under the DefinitionShape
344 class) into sets of boundary surface polygons (B-reps). These polygons follow the outward normal
345 convention, where the normal vectors of all boundary surface polygons point outward from the
346 solid. At the end of this step, the element checking pairs, along with the defined checking operation
347 type in the input, and the generated boundary surface sets, form separate computation threads
348 to be executed in the next core step.
- 349 2. Main checking operations: The computational threads formed in step 1, which contain the ele-
350 ments to be checked, their corresponding boundary surface sets, and the checking operation type,
351 are executed in parallel. The algorithmic processes of these checking operations are described
352 analytically in [40].
- 353 3. Output: The results of the checking operations performed in parallel during step 2 are compiled
354 into an output, which can be either a native XML file, an OBJ file for visual inspection, or a BCF
355 file for BIM collaboration.

356 GRC aims to be an extremely fast checker, which is why it is implemented in C++ and utilizes mul-
 357 tithreading by assigning different element pairs to separate processor cores for checking. To accelerate
 358 the processing operations further, GRC handles the clash-dependent and time-consuming operations
 359 (such as clash and containment) differently from the less demanding operations (like adjacency).

360 For the clash-dependent operations, GRC does not rely on proximity criteria (like distance) to
 361 eliminate certain pairs from consideration. Instead, it only checks element pairs whose Axis Aligned
 362 Bounding Boxes (AABBs) intersect. AABB clash detection involves minimal multiplications and condi-
 363 tion checks compared to standard clash detection, making it significantly faster. When AABBs intersect,
 364 regular clash detection is then performed using Binary Space Partitioning (BSP) trees (see [41]). To
 365 further optimize computation time, GRC calculates and preloads the BSP trees and AABBs of all el-
 366 ements during the Boundary Surface Extraction (Step 1) into memory for use in the clash-dependent
 367 operations.

368 The execution time of GRC depends on the number of element pairs to be checked and the resolution
 369 of the elements (i.e., the average number of boundary surfaces per element). As demonstrated in the
 370 following application section, with this implementation, GRC can conduct clash-dependent operations
 371 on millions of element pairs of relatively moderate geometric resolution, within a matter of minutes.

372 3.4. GRC accuracy

373 The accuracy of the GRC is influenced by the complexity of the solids that are being checked. As
 374 outlined in [40], the clash and containment checks performed by GRC rely on set operations (inter-
 375 section) on polyhedra using Binary Space Partitioning (BSP) trees, that are created through polygon
 376 clipping operations in three dimensions. These clipping operations (implemented using [42]) involve
 377 pairs of polygons in 3D space, where one acts as the clipping polygon and the other as the clipped
 378 polygon. The accuracy of these operations is determined by the angle between the normal vectors of
 379 these polygons. The closer this angle is to zero degrees, the less accurate this clipping operation is.
 380 Consequently, the accuracy of GRC operations decreases when neighboring polygons in the boundary
 381 representations become nearly coplanar. Such conditions often occur in polyhedral solid boundary rep-
 382 resentations (b-reps) with low gradient values at their edge points (i.e., b-reps with smooth boundary
 383 surfaces). Therefore, the GRC’s clash and containment detection is expected to be less accurate for
 384 solids with smooth boundary surfaces compared to those with sharper edges.

385 For performing geometric operations at different scales, particularly for adjacency checks, it is essen-
 386 tial to establish a coplanarity condition for polygon pairs. This condition should be defined by an angle
 387 and distance threshold across all GRC operations. This coplanarity condition and the related distance
 388 and angle thresholds is a prerequisite for the GRC adjacency checks as described next. Adjacency
 389 checks involve pairwise polygon checks, as illustrated for polygons A and B in Figure 4. Specifically,
 390 each boundary representation polygon of the first solid is checked with a corresponding boundary repre-
 391 sentation polygon of the second solid, as outlined by the function F_{cos} found in [40]. The angle threshold
 392 for these checks is defined as the allowable deviation from 180 degrees between the normal vectors of
 393 the two checked polygons. If this deviation is within this threshold, the polygons are deemed to be
 394 parallel with opposite orientations. This angle threshold is Φ^{th} , as illustrated in Figure 4. The detected
 395 parallel polygons with opposite orientations form candidate polygon pairs. For each candidate pair, the
 396 maximum distance between a point on one polygon and the plane of the other (plane-to-point distance)
 397 is checked against the distance threshold. Using the previously defined angle and distance thresholds
 398 and according to Figure 4, adjacency is detected if three conditions are met: (a) the polygons are par-
 399 allel ($\phi < \Phi^{th}$) with opposite orientations, (b) the maximum point-to-plane distance remains below the
 400 distance threshold ($d_{max} < D^{th}$), and (c) the projections of the polygons intersect on a plane parallel
 401 to either one of the polygons’ planes (see Figure 4). When these criteria are satisfied, the polygons
 402 and the respective solids are considered adjacent. In case only a and b are satisfied the polygons are
 403 considered coplanar without being adjacent.

Figure 4: Illustration of angle and distance tolerance thresholds, used in adjacency relations.

404 3.5. GRC ontology

405 To store the obtained GRC results in a knowledge graph form (step 4 of the methodology presented
 406 in Figure 1), we introduce an initial draft of a grc ontology that uses a single `grc:SolidModel` class
 407 as illustrated with a blue box in the block diagram of Figure 5. As displayed in this figure, the grc
 408 ontology has bindings with classes from the brick [39] (`brick:Equipment`) and FSO ontologies [43]
 409 (`fso:Component` and `fso:Segment`), via the `grc:hasSolidModel` relationship. Additional links of the
 410 `grc:SolidModel` class with the `geom:Geometry` class of the Ontology of Geometric Primitives [34] via
 411 the `grc:hasGeometry` relation, can be established. Depending on the detected geometric relationship,
 412 each `grc:SolidModel` instance is connected with another `grc:SolidModel` instance. If adjacency or
 413 clash is detected, the two `grc:SolidModel` instances are connected with the `grc:isAdjacentTo` or
 414 `grc:intersectsWith` relationship, respectively. If containment is detected, the `grc:SolidModel` in-
 415 stances are connected with the `grc:isContainedIn` or `grc:contains` relationships.

Figure 5: UML diagram of GRC ontology and its links to REC and FSO ontologies.

416 4. Application in MEP fluid transfer networks

417 In this section, we showcase how geometric relationships among the solid geometric representations
418 of BIM elements can lead to the discovery of missing BIM element relations and their corresponding
419 knowledge graph links (logical relations). This approach is applied explicitly to data within the build-
420 ing MEP domain because the BIM elements have complex geometric representations. The approach
421 can be easily extended to other domains, such as architecture, where the geometrical representations
422 are simpler. While geometric relations can be utilized to unveil desired BIM element relations [38],
423 it's important to note that not all existing BIM element relations can be identified using geometric
424 methods due to various reasons [44],[45]. Recent research efforts have been increasingly directed to-
425 wards generating MEP topology in knowledge graph format from BIM data, leveraging BIM geometric
426 representations [38],[46], as well as employing rule checking and subgraph matching techniques [47].
427 Moreover, the geometric relations identified through this process can be employed to uncover design
428 errors, such as clashes among the geometric representations of MEP elements.

429 Within BIM models, various interconnected MEP elements form distinct fluid transfer networks. The
430 fluid being transferred could be categorized as air or gas, water, waste, or electricity. These elements
431 serve three primary roles within their networks: they are either source elements, distribution elements,
432 or terminal elements. Source elements produce fluid resources, distribution elements transfer them, and
433 terminal elements consume them. The proposed workflow aims to facilitate the generation of knowledge
434 graphs that depict the connections of MEP fluid transfer networks. This is achieved by identifying
435 missing semantics in BIM data through the geometric relationships among the solid representations of
436 BIM MEP elements and building space volumes. Before delving into how these missing semantics can
437 be inferred, the complete MEP fluid transfer network and its BIM data requirements are defined in the
438 subsequent subsections.

439 4.1. Complete MEP fluid transfer network

440 From a data completeness perspective, three conditions should be satisfied for an MEP transfer fluid
441 network to be complete:

- 442 1. All MEP terminal elements should be fed into a building space.
- 443 2. Source elements should be connected with terminal elements via a series of distribution elements.
- 444 3. A flow relation should be defined for every network edge connection between source and terminal
445 elements.

446 4.2. BIM Data requirements

447 To generate the previously defined complete MEP fluid transfer networks using data from BIM data
448 sources, the available BIM data should satisfy the following conditions:

- 449 1. All MEP elements should have solid geometric representations.
- 450 2. The solid geometric representations of the connected MEP elements should share common bound-
451 ary surfaces or intersect with each other.
- 452 3. At least one element at every edge of the MEP knowledge graph should have a predefined flow
453 direction.
- 454 4. The geometric representations of MEP terminal units should intersect with at least one building
455 space volume.

456 *4.3. Primary and derived knowledge gaps*

457 To construct a comprehensive MEP fluid transfer network, it's essential to explore the available
 458 information within a BIM model. This information can be categorized into two distinct "knowledge
 459 sets": the primary knowledge set and the derived knowledge set. The primary knowledge set comprises
 460 information specified by the BIM designer and exported within the BIM model. This data is indis-
 461 pensable for creating a complete MEP fluid transfer network and cannot be deduced from other related
 462 data. Conversely, the derived knowledge set encompasses information that can be inferred from other
 463 data contained within the primary knowledge set. Any gaps in the primary knowledge dataset may
 464 lead to violations of the conditions outlined in the preceding subsection.

465 Examples of gaps in both primary and derived knowledge data are depicted in Figure 6 for a serial
 466 connection of three pipe segments: A, B, and C. In part A of Figure 6, an entire pipe segment (Segment
 467 B) is absent from the BIM data. This segment serves to connect pipe segments A and C, making the
 468 knowledge of segment B crucial for generating a comprehensive knowledge graph. Thus, the absence
 469 of segment B serves as an instance of a primary knowledge gap, violating condition 2 of the data
 470 requirements outlined in the previous subsection.

471 In the example shown in part B of Figure 6, although the geometric representation of segment B
 472 exists within the BIM model, the semantic connections between segments A and B, and between B and
 473 C, are not explicitly contained in the BIM data. In this scenario, these absent semantic connections can
 474 be inferred using geometric operations on the solid geometric representations of the involved elements.
 475 These missing connections represent an instance of a derived knowledge gap since they can be uncovered
 476 using geometric methods. By identifying and generating such missing semantic links (illustrated in red
 477 in Figure 6), the completeness of the MEP knowledge graph and the respective MEP fluid transfer
 478 network can be restored.

Figure 6: Primary and derived knowledge gap examples.

479 After presenting the BIM data requirements two BIM relation types will be discussed in the following
 480 subsection. These relation types will play a fundamental role in the formation of complete MEP transfer
 481 fluid networks.

482 *4.4. MEP relation types*

483 This work considers two distinct types of BIM relations involving MEP elements and their cor-
 484 responding building space volumes: connectivity relations among the MEP elements themselves and
 485 containment relations between the MEP elements and the volumes of their building spaces. These two
 486 types of BIM relations and their associations with geometric and semantic relations are elaborated upon
 487 in the subsequent subsections.

488 4.4.1. MEP connectivity

489 Each element within an MEP network, whether it's a source, sink, or distribution element, is linked
 490 to another element within the same network. This connection manifests in three distinct contexts:
 491 within a BIM framework, a geometric framework, and a knowledge graph framework. The connectivity
 492 of MEP elements is represented in BIM files through specific class relationships between pairs of con-
 493 nected elements, as depicted in part A of Figure 7. The BIM connectivity relation, which represents a
 494 topological relation, is implemented through the `IfcRelConnectsPorts` relation within the openBIM IFC
 495 schema.

496 In a geometric context, the solid geometric representations of connected MEP elements either share
 497 common boundary surfaces or slightly intersect, meaning their solid volumes have a relatively small
 498 common part. In this context, MEP connectivity is established either as a geometric adjacency relation
 499 (as depicted in part B of Figure 7) or a geometric clash relation. The adjacency relation is exem-
 500 plified in part B of Figure 7 by the grey circular surfaces, which represent the common boundaries
 501 between the geometric representations of the pipe, the boiler, and the sanitary terminal units. Lastly,
 502 the MEP connectivity relation can be articulated as a topological relation within a knowledge graph
 503 context. This is demonstrated in part C of Figure 7, where knowledge graph links are established us-
 504 ing the `fso:connectedWith` relation (defined in the `fso` ontology [43]), linking a `brick:boiler` class
 505 element and a `brick:Equipment` class element via a `fso:Segment` class element (defined in the `fso`
 506 ontology [43]). In case the proposed `grc` ontology is used the predicates `grc:intersects` and
 507 `grc:isAdjacentTo` should be mapped to the predicate `fso:connectedWith` when both subject object
 508 object refer to a MEP distribution element.

Figure 7: Connectivity expressed using three relation types: (A) BIM, (B) Geometric, and (C) Knowledge graph.

509 Although the MEP connectivity relations, in knowledge graph terms, can be induced in a straight-
 510 forward manner from the connectivity relations in a BIM context, this is not valid for the connectivity
 511 relations in a geometric context. For example, if two elements are geometrically adjacent to each other
 512 (their solid geometric representations share a common boundary surface) or intersect with each other
 513 (their solid geometric representations share common solid volumes), are not necessarily connected in a
 514 BIM, or a knowledge graph context, and vice versa. This inconsistency is due to errors in the involved
 515 manual design and BIM exportation processes, that produce the geometrical representations of the

MEP elements. Table 1 presents different cases of geometric and BIM connectivity relation scenarios. According to table 1, if two elements are geometrically connected (their solid representations are adjacent or intersect) and are not connected in BIM, there is either a BIM design/modeling error or the two elements are adjacent to each other without being connected (false positive case). Finally, if two elements are connected in the BIM and not geometrically connected (there is no adjacency or clash), there is a BIM design/modeling error or a BIM exporter error, causing the geometrical representations of the elements to clash with each other or to be far apart (false negative case).

Table 1: Confusion matrix related to connectivity relation detection in geometric and BIM contexts.

Geometric Adjacency/Clash \ BIM Connectivity	Yes	No
	Yes	(Issue free)
No	Design/Modeling or exporter error (false negative)	(Issue free)

4.4.2. MEP-space containment

The different MEP elements found within the BIM data may be associated with a particular building space. This association is depicted in BIM models through specific class relationships. For example, in IFC models, as demonstrated in part A of Figure 8, a containment relationship is defined between the classes `IfcBoiler` and `IfcSpace`, indicated by the `IfcRelContainedInSpatialStructure` connection. This relationship can also be represented in knowledge graph terms using the predicate `brick:isLocationOf` from the `brick` ontology as illustrated by the triplet displayed in part C of Figure 8. In this example, the predicate links the subject `brick:Space` (which is assigned to the `IfcSpace` class) to the object `brick:Boiler` (which is assigned to the `IfcBoiler` class). Finally, these connections can be identified through geometric clash and containment detection procedures applied to the solid geometric representations of the elements involved (such as the volumes of the building space and its contained element). As illustrated in the example provided in part B of Figure 8, the solid geometric representations of the boiler and the space volumes intersect, indicating a geometric containment relation (where the boiler solid is entirely within the volume of the space solid). If the MEP element does not fit fully inside the space volume, the intended containment relation can still be identified using geometric clash detection instead of geometric containment detection. For this reason, if the proposed `grc` ontology is used, the predicates `grc:isContainedIn` and `grc:intersectsWith` should be assigned to the predicate `brick:isLocationOf` if the subject refers to a building space and the object to a MEP terminal unit or system.

As in the case of the adjacency relations detected in BIM, for the containment relations, there are four possible cases where the geometric clash or containment relation and the containment in BIM might or might not be present. These cases are illustrated in table 2. According to table 2, if an MEP terminal element is contained in a space volume in a geometric sense (their respective geometric solid representations intersect, forming a clash or a containment, where one volume is contained inside the other) and there are no respective containment relations in the BIM model, then there is a BIM design/modeling error related to these elements (false positive case). Finally, if an MEP terminal unit is connected, via a containment relation in the BIM model, with one building space, but there is no containment or clash relation in the geometric sense (their geometric representations do not intersect), there is a design/modeling error or a BIM exporter error, causing the geometrical representations of the MEP and space elements to be far apart (false negative case).

Figure 8: Containment expressed using three relation types: (A) BIM, (B) Geometric, and (C) Knowledge graph.

Table 2: Confusion matrix related to containment relation detection in geometric and BIM contexts.

Geometric Containment/Clash	BIM Containment	
	Yes	No
Yes	(Issue free)	Design/Modeling error (false positive)
No	Design/Modeling or exporter error (false negative)	(Issue free)

553 4.5. Correlation between BIM relations and Geometric relations

554 Based on the discussion of the previous sections, a BIM relation may involve one or more geomet-
 555 ric relations. More specifically, one or more of the above geometric relations (adjacency, clash, and
 556 containment) can be used to reveal BIM semantic relations (connectivity and containment) among
 557 BIM elements. Table 3 illustrates the correlation between BIM connectivity and containment semantic
 558 relations and respective geometric relations.

Table 3: Connections between BIM semantic relations and Geometric relations

Geometric relation	BIM relation	
	Connectivity	Containment
Adjacency	✓	
Clash	✓	✓
Containment		✓

559 In conclusion, as shown in part A of Figure 9, a well-designed MEP BIM produces a semantic
 560 connectivity and containment knowledge graph - based on the fso and brick ontologies according to
 561 part C in Figures 7 and 8 - that aligns with a corresponding geometric relation knowledge graph based
 562 on the grc ontology, except from the geometric adjacency links that correspond to elements that are
 563 adjacent with respect to geometry but not connected in semantic terms. Specifically, each edge in the
 564 semantic graph (displayed in blue in Figure 9 indicating connectivity or containment) matches an edge
 565 in the grc-based graph (displayed in red in Figure 9 indicating adjacency, clash, or containment) and
 566 connects the same elements, apart from the aforementioned geometric adjacent relations. The red dots

567 in Figure 9 indicate `grc:SolidModel` classes and the blue dots in the same figure indicate brick or fso
 568 classes related to physical objects (`brick:Equipment`, `fso:Segment`, ...). In graph theory terms this
 569 graph alignment can be expressed as: $\mathcal{G}_s = \{V_s, E_s\} \subseteq \{V_g, E_g\} = \mathcal{G}_g$, where V is the set of graph nodes,
 570 E is the set of graph edges, \mathcal{G}_g is the grc graph and \mathcal{G}_s is the semantic (fso and brick based) graph.
 571 In contrast, as illustrated in part B of Figure 9, mismatches between these graphs can typically be
 572 attributed to BIM design/modeling errors (false positives, $E_g \setminus E_s$) or errors in BIM design, modelling
 573 or export processes (false negatives, $E_s \setminus E_g$).

Figure 9: Correlation between design/modeling errors and knowledge graph misalignment.

574 4.6. Geometry-induced knowledge graph establishment

575 This section investigates how previous geometric relations (adjacency, clash, and containment),
 576 which are correlated to MEP connectivity and containment relations, can be used for the formation of
 577 a geometry-induced knowledge graph among the elements in MEP-BIM models. This graph formation
 578 involves two stages, the GRC-based workflow stage and an ontology stage.

579 4.6.1. GRC-based workflow for BIM relation inference

580 A GRC-based workflow was proposed to identify the existing connections among MEP entities in
 581 the MEP-IFC files. It has three stages to extract the connectivity pairs by checking the BIM context,
 582 executing the GRC tool, and implementing axis-aligned bounding boxes (AABB) checking operation.
 583 Figure 10 illustrates the key steps in each stage.

Figure 10: Diagram of the proposed GRC-based workflow.

584 *Connectivity relations*

585 This workflow initially identifies all semantic connections by checking `IfcRelConnectsPorts` in the
586 IFC file, generating a list of connectivity pairs. Subsequently, the GRC tool uncovers additional geo-
587 metric relationships among the MEP elements and then exports the clash/adjacency pairs to create the
588 connectivity pairs. Meanwhile, the GRC tool detects elements with geometric surface errors. To avoid
589 incorrect GRC detections, the pairs of elements that have geometric errors, are forwarded to AABB
590 checking to detect additional potential connectivity relations. Finally, all connectivity pairs are merged
591 to facilitate the extraction of most linked pairs from IFC files, which provides the linking entities in the
592 geometry-induced MEP knowledge graphs.

593 *Containment relations*

594 Containment relationships are common in BIM models, particularly between systems (e.g., AHUs,
595 FCUs, MVHRs) and spaces, as well as between terminals (e.g., diffusers, grilles, radiators, door heaters)
596 and spaces. However, these containment relations cannot be inferred solely through the BIM context
597 or AABB checking. Only the GRC tool can reliably infer them by examining (2nd stage of Figure 10)
598 potential clash and containment relationships between the geometric representations of spaces and MEP
599 systems and terminal units. The containment pairs generated at this stage help to identify terminal
600 and system locations within the building’s spatial layout. These pairs, along with connectivity pairs,
601 are then used to create geometry-based MEP knowledge graphs.

602 *4.6.2. Ontology mapping*

603 Ontologies offer a comprehensive means to semantically describe all the elements and their rela-
604 tionship within the architectural and MEP domains. In this work, two ontologies were introduced
605 and integrated to cover the MEP elements as much as possible. `brickSchema` [39], developed by Brick
606 Consortium, effectively delineates building assets and their interconnections, especially within the archi-
607 tectural domain. As a supplement, `Flow Systems Ontology (FSO)` [43], concentrating on interconnected
608 systems and energy flow connections, was introduced to represent the pipework and ductwork segments.
609 Table 4 illustrates the mapping relationship between IFC classes and ontologies. Regarding the three
610 geometric relationships between the MEP elements, `fso:connectedWith` indicates the connectivity
611 relations (clash and adjacency), and `brick:isLocationOf` indicates the containment relations. To
612 prevent naming conflicts, the IFC global ID (GUID) was used to represent each MEP element in the
613 geometry-induced knowledge graphs.

614 Finally, it is important to note that when HVAC systems or terminal units are described by the generic
615 `IfcBuildingElementProxy` class, they cannot be identified as HVAC terminal or system elements,
616 which introduces additional challenges in generating the final MEP knowledge graph. However, in cer-
617 tain cases, specific properties of a system or terminal unit may be available, assisting in its identification.

618 **5. Examples**

619 *5.1. Overview*

620 We demonstrate the application of the introduced GRC tool based methodology, on the MEP system
621 of the Podium of the One Pool Street (OPS) building on the University College London campus. The
622 building incorporates a sophisticated Mechanical Ventilation System designed to meet specific require-
623 ments. This system ensures the circulation of fresh, tempered, or cooled air throughout the building’s
624 spaces while simultaneously removing exhaust air. These functions are facilitated by air handling units,
625 which are integral to the building’s infrastructure and are linked to both the Low-Temperature Hot
626 Water (LTHW) heating system and the Chilled Water (CHW) system. The LTHW Heating System
627 provides heat, while the Chilled Water System offers cooling, contributing to a comfortable indoor
628 environment.

Table 4: Mapping between IFC and Ontology classes.

IFC class	Ontology:Class
IfcSpace	brick:Space
IfcChiller	brick:Chiller
IfcHeatExchanger	brick:HX
IfcBoiler	brick:Boiler
IfcAirTerminal	brick:Air_Diffuser
IfcFan	brick:Fan
IfcDuctSegment	fso:Segment
IfcDuctFitting	fso:Fitting
IfcPipeSegment	fso:Segment
IfcPipeFitting	fso:Fitting
IfcFlowMeter	brick:Meter
IfcValve	brick:Valve
IfcWasteTerminal	brick:Equipment

IfcUnitaryEquipment (PredefinedType)	brick:AHU
	brick:DOAS
	brick:FCU

IfcAirTerminalBox	brick:VAV
IfcSpaceHeater	brick:Radiator
IfcRelConnectsPorts	fso:connectedWith
IfcRelContainedInSpatialStructure	brick:isLocationOf

629 The air handling units feature heat/cool recovery mechanisms, which extract energy from exhaust
630 air, subsequently reducing the heating and cooling demands placed on the system via VAV boxes or
631 constant air volume diffusers. Additionally, Mechanical Ventilation Heat Recovery (MVHR) units are
632 strategically positioned to distribute air directly to various areas within the building. These units are
633 interconnected with ceiling diffusers or fan coil units via a network of ductwork.

634 Furthermore, the building's Chilled Water Service (CHWS) is facilitated by an air-cooled chiller,
635 which plays a crucial role in cooling the fresh air circulated by the air handling units. The CHWS
636 system includes cooling coils within the air handling units and fan coil units dispersed throughout
637 the building. These fan coil units not only recirculate the supply air but also further cool it before
638 distributing it through secondary ductwork to ceiling diffusers. In terms of heating, the LTHW Heating
639 System receives heat energy from a District Heating System and plate heat exchangers. This system
640 provides warmth to the building's Podium via heater batteries located within the air handling units and
641 fan coil units. Additionally, it serves to temper the supply of air provided by the Mechanical Ventilation
642 Systems. Radiators, warm air curtains, over-door heaters, and heat interface units (HIUs) also leverage
643 the LTHW Heating System to provide localized heating to specific areas within the building. Figure 11
644 presents the architectural model of the building and its HVAC schematic diagram. Similarly, Figure 12
645 displays the visualization of the selected and exported IFC Architectural and MEP content.

646 Complementing these systems is the Mains Cold Water Service (MCWS), which is distributed to the
647 building's Sprinkler System tank and a main bulk storage tank. A Booster Cold Water Service (BCWS)

a) ARC-BIM model of OPS podium

b) Schematic diagram of HVAC system in OPS podium

Figure 11: a) 3D visualization of OPS podium, and b) schematic diagram of its HVAC system.

648 is then delivered to various points within the building, including the Hot Water Service. Booster sets
 649 equipped with electromagnetic water conditioning devices ensure efficient water distribution throughout
 650 the building, with each floor served by a dedicated branch of the BCWS.

651 Lastly, the building's Above Ground Rainwater Drainage Systems consist of strategically installed
 652 rainwater outlets located on the roof and terrace areas. These outlets discharge rainwater into Below
 653 Ground Rainwater Drainage Systems, which are installed by the Main Contractor, completing the
 654 building's comprehensive water management infrastructure.

655 5.2. Data processing

656 An ideal scenario entails inputting one solitary MEP-IFC file into the GRC workflow to establish
 657 an HVAC knowledge graph. However, the nature of the input geometric data, characterized by LOD
 658 300-400 granularity, poses a challenge due to memory issues when parsing and checking large IFC files.
 659 More specifically, the number of pair checks for N elements grows polynomially ($O(N^2)$) (for N elements,
 660 the number of pair checks is $\frac{N(N-1)}{2}$). In the application example, $N \approx 20,000$, and thus the number
 661 of pair checks approaches 200 million pairs. Consequently, dividing the large complete MEP-IFC file
 662 into three smaller IFC files becomes necessary: two IFC files for the HVAC domain and one IFC file for
 663 the non-HVAC domain. The HVAC-related IFC files are for the air-loop elements and the water-loop
 664 elements (heating and cooling purposes), respectively. The non-HVAC IFC file covers the pipework
 665 elements for domestic hot/cold water systems and rainwater/drainage systems. This splitting approach
 666 can reduce the inputted IFC files with minimum manual work. Figure 12 illustrates the ARC-BIM and
 667 MEP-BIM models in Revit, and the exported IFC files are shown as well.

668 5.3. MEP knowledge graph establishment

669 This work uses a building-oriented ontology, named BrickSchema, to develop MEP knowledge graphs
 670 for achieving error detection, bridging from air terminals to systems, and splitting the MEP models into
 671 different domains. To accomplish a number of processing steps using the GRC process, are required, as
 672 outlined in the following subsections.

673 5.3.1. Error detection and path-finding

674 This GRC tool-based workflow can identify the majority of the connections among MEP elements,
 675 but some of them might be missing due to the data quality of the input MEP-IFC files. To ensure
 676 the completeness and accuracy of the generated MEP graph, it is essential to pinpoint the existing and
 677 potential issues/errors in the IFC file. For these reasons, a set of error detection rules for MEP elements
 678 are presented in the next Table 5 (links may represent a "Clash", an "Adjacency", or a "Containment"
 679 in the case of IfcSpace elements), is established.

680 When MEP graphs are generated, error detection can be performed to pinpoint the precise location
 681 and type of errors in the provided IFC files. In the OPS building podium case study, five error types
 682 were identified: a) abnormal clash, b) missing element, c) geometric mismatch, d) classification error,

Figure 12: Object selection in ARC/MEP Revit models and IFC exportation.

Table 5: Error detection rules for MEP elements.

MEP element	Rule
IfcPipeSegment	< 2 linked elements
IfcPipeFitting	< 2 linked elements
IfcDuctSegment	< 2 linked elements
IfcDuctFitting	< 2 linked elements
IfcValve	< 2 linked elements
IfcFlowMeter	< 2 linked elements
IfcPipeSegment	linked to (≥ 1) IfcDuctSegment
IfcPipeSegment	linked to (≥ 1) IfcDuctFitting
IfcPipeFitting	linked to (≥ 1) IfcDuctSegment
IfcPipeFitting	linked to (≥ 1) IfcDuctFitting
IfcAirTerminal	linked to (0 or > 2) IfcDuctSegment
IfcAirTerminal	linked to (0 or > 2) IfcSpace
IfcSpaceHeater	linked to (0 or > 2) IfcSpace

683 and e) Space containment issue, as illustrated in Figure 13. Many of these errors originate from
684 inaccuracies in manual modeling during the design phase, bugs during the IFC exporting process or
685 during the extraction of MEP models from the comprehensive federal BIM model of the entire building.
686 Despite the identification and localization of errors, manual intervention is still required for resolution.
687 One approach involves directly adding missing links or deleting incorrect ones in the MEP graph.
688 Alternatively, the IFC file can be refined and corrected, and the updated version can be re-imported
689 into the GRC-based workflow.

690 However, certain potential and elusive issues cannot be directly identified using the aforementioned
691 rules. Therefore, this study introduces the path-finding approach, using depth-first search algorithms
692 to further detect such issues. This approach should be implemented after the initial establishment of

Figure 13: Case study's BIM error classification: a) abnormal clash, b) missing element, c) Geometric mismatch, d) Classification error, and e) Space containment issue.

693 the MEP graphs. Figure 14 illustrates the accuracy of the air-loop MEP knowledge graph established
 694 through this GRC-based workflow, which includes the application of initial error detection and fixes
 695 based on the aforementioned rules, and a final path-finding process. The results of the overall method
 696 are displayed in parts a and b in Figure 14. Part a) reveals that over 95% of the air terminals (Dif-
 697 fusers/grilles) were correctly linked to their corresponding systems (AHU/FCU/MVHR). About 2.2%
 698 of the air terminals were linked to two or three systems, with some supplied by FCUs linked to an
 699 MVHR in series, which is not a common design approach. A few of these instances were attributed
 700 to checking issues arising from adjacent duct entities that are not physically connected. Furthermore,
 701 the remaining 2.8% were not linked to any systems due to irregular human design errors in ductwork
 702 and relevant accessories. These results were verified using the building's HVAC schematic drawings.
 703 Through manual intervention for error resolution, all air terminals can achieve the correct systems using
 704 the path-finding approach, details of which are available in the following subsection.

Part b) of Figure 14 illustrates the precision of the link (containment relation) between spaces and air terminals. About 70% of the air terminals are accurately matched with their designated spaces. However, around 18.5% remain unassociated with any space due to certain spaces not extending high enough to reach the ceiling surfaces and several missing spaces on the terrace. Additionally, surface errors in air terminals were identified during the execution of the GRC tool, triggering the activation of bounding-box checking that resulted in the creation of a few non-existent links. Consequently, manual correction was required to eliminate the non-existent links, affecting approximately 9.5% of the air terminals, which were erroneously connected to two or more spaces.

Figure 14: Distribution of air terminals linked to: a) systems and b) spaces.

5.3.2. Geometry-induced MEP knowledge graph

After completing the error resolution process, a thorough and precise MEP knowledge graph is constructed, containing the interconnections among MEP elements. This graph is defined as the Geometry-induced MEP Knowledge Graph. To delve into the structural aspects of the generated graph, the following paragraphs analyze parts of the graph related to three data domains: air loops, HVAC-related water loops, and non-HVAC water loops.

5.3.2.1 MEP knowledge graph for air loops

Utilizing path-finding queries within the established Geometry-induced MEP knowledge graph facilitates the extraction of structural features and linkage information within MEP systems. Figure 15 visually showcases the outcomes of querying air loops in BlenderBIM. The components involved, such as AHUs, their associated air terminals, and relevant ducts, were extracted to form their ventilation subsystems. Notably, many ventilation subsystems span multiple floors and areas, incorporating Variable Air Volume (VAV) boxes. Additionally, over fifty ventilation subsystems, driven by MVHRs and FCUs, were identified and extracted, although they are not visualized due to their simpler and smaller-scale structures. Compared to manual methods, graph-based queries expedite information extraction and system partitioning. This capability enhances the structural information integrated into the building management system and proves advantageous in identifying faults during operational issues.

Figure 15: Extraction of connection elements among AHUs and their air terminals, from the full air-loop IFC data set.

732 *5.3.2.2 MEP knowledge graph for HVAC-related water loops*

733 Path-finding queries in the generated Geometry-induced MEP knowledge graph can also reveal HVAC-
 734 related water loop components and their networks. In the considered building example, the OPS podium
 735 is serviced by an air-cooled chiller and district heating systems via main water pipes originating from a
 736 service building (energy station). Consequently, this study initiated queries using the connection points
 737 between the primary water loop and secondary water loops as starting points, deviating from the use of
 738 energy source components (e.g., HIUs or Chillers). Figure 16 visually demonstrates the MEP networks
 739 formed from the graph queries, with the related water-loop IFC model split into two distinct domains:
 740 Low-Temperature Hot Water (LTHW) and Chilled Water (CHW). The analysis reveals that the LTHW
 741 system comprises only one secondary loop, while the CHW system incorporates two. Half of the AHUs
 742 are connected to both water loops, while the remaining half exclusively links to the LTHW loop. Ad-
 743 ditionally, all FCUs are connected to the CHW system, with 83% of them also having connections to
 744 the LTHW loop. This configuration aligns with the schematic drawings.

745

746 *5.3.2.3 MEP knowledge graph for non-HVAC water loops*

747 Non-HVAC water loop networks, including domestic water pipework, rainwater pipework, and drainage
 748 pipework, were included in the input IFC model of the GRC process. By employing a query-based
 749 extraction process, similar to HVAC-related water loops, three water loops were formed that include: a
 750 domestic hot water loop, a domestic cold water loop, and a rainwater and drainage pipework, as shown
 751 in Figure 17. Unlike the HVAC domain, most terminals in these domestic cold/hot water loops (such
 752 as water taps or showers) were absent in the raw data. Consequently, despite the detection of numerous
 753 errors through the aforementioned rules, these discrepancies can be overlooked without necessitating
 754 revisions in the geometry-induced MEP knowledge graph. Furthermore, if an MEP element is not
 755 associated with any of the aforementioned loops, it can be classified as rainwater or drainage pipework.
 756 This is because these domains lack a clear loop structure, and such information is far less crucial than

Extract the LTHW and CHW loops from the geometry-induced knowledge graph

Figure 16: Extraction of LTHW loop and CHW loop connection elements, from the full HVAC-related and water-loop IFC data set.

757 in the HVAC domain when considering building energy modelling.

Figure 17: Extraction of domestic hot/cold water loop, rainwater and drainage pipework elements from the full whole non-HVAC and water-loop IFC data set.

758 Ultimately, the establishment of a geometry-induced MEP knowledge graph and the application
759 of queries have led to a clear and structured representation of MEP systems. This approach holds

760 the potential to significantly facilitate the development of building digital twins and enhance building
 761 management systems.

762 *5.3.3. Breakdown of GRC results and graph evolution*

763 The diagram in Figure 18 showcases the distribution of connectivity pairs across three IFC files, origi-
 764 nating from four stages within the GRC-based workflow: BIM context, GRC tool, BBOX, and manual
 765 intervention. Notably, the number of pairs from the BIM context in air loops is notably lower compared
 766 to water loops, attributed to MEP fabrication elements lacking semantic linking. This emphasizes the
 767 pivotal role of the GRC tool in identifying air-loop connections. Bounding-box checking remains vital,
 768 as it identifies roughly 40% connectivity pairs due to issues like non-face-to-face connections and surface
 769 errors. Concerning HVAC-related water loops, the BIM context contributes nearly 80% connectivity
 770 pairs, with 13% from the GRC tool and less than 9% from bounding-box checking, mainly due to unsup-
 771 ported geometric representations and human errors near AHUs/FCUs. Furthermore, the combination
 772 of the BIM context and the GRC tool effectively manages elements in non-HVAC water loops, given
 773 their simpler geometric representations.

Figure 18: Distribution of the connectivity pairs obtained from different stages in the GRC-based workflow.

774 Figure 19 presents geometry-induced MEP knowledge graphs for HVAC-related air and water loops,
 775 illustrating their progressive enrichment at each stage. In the enrichment process for the HVAC air loops
 776 (top row), BIM designers employed fabrication duct elements, assembling them into ductwork without
 777 semantic links, resulting in a very sparse initial graph with few linked entities. Introducing the GRC tool
 778 notably improved ductwork network completeness, filling numerous missing links. Subsequently, BIM
 779 elements with surface errors were checked using bounding boxes, further enhancing graph completeness.
 780 A ruleset check corrected certain problematic entities, completing the graph establishment. The number
 781 of links detected at each stage can be found in Figure 18. Unlike the air loop, the HVAC water loop
 782 graph (bottom row) showed more complete BIM semantic links due to fewer fabrication pipes, allowing
 783 most link relationships to be directly extracted. Enrichment through GRC and bounding boxes provided

784 a fully comprehensive graph, as shown in the final graph, demonstrating that the proportion of detected
 785 links is related to BIM data quality.

786 Overall, achieving full automation of geometric relation checking poses challenges due to the varied
 787 nature of MEP-BIM files and their inconsistent data quality. The proposed GRC-based workflow
 788 addresses this challenge by pinpointing errors/issues, significantly speeding up the establishment of the
 789 knowledge graph, and ensuring its overall completeness.

Figure 19: Visualization of the geometry-induced MEP knowledge graphs enriched through the GRC-based workflow.

790 6. Discussion

791 The proposed geometric methodology is applied to MEP HVAC and ARC BIM data with the goal
 792 of identifying connections between HVAC source and sink devices, as well as determining the locations
 793 of HVAC terminal devices within the building’s spatial volumes. The main objective of this approach
 794 is to create an HVAC connection graph that facilitates the automatic generation of building energy
 795 performance simulation models. This work is differentiated from existing methods in the literature,
 796 which focus on clash detection and adjacency identification for BIM quality checks and code compliance.

797 Additionally, as demonstrated in the large and complex application example involving HVAC net-
 798 works for air, hot water, and cold water transfer in the podium of UCL’s One Pool Street building, the
 799 proposed methodology successfully infers connections between HVAC source and sink components, as
 800 well as containments between HVAC terminal units and building spaces, in a relatively short time (a
 801 few hours). This relatively short execution time, is achieved despite the need to evaluate millions of
 802 element pairs for thousands of components, all without any prior knowledge of any connections.

803 GRC is domain-agnostic and can be applied to geometric data from various fields, such as architec-
 804 ture. For instance, adjacent surfaces between building walls and slabs can reveal thermal bridges, which
 805 are critical for building energy performance simulations to assess thermal losses. Furthermore, GRC

806 can be utilized across different domains, as demonstrated in this study with ARC and MEP data. This
807 capability is especially valuable for breaking down siloed data approaches, allowing for cross-domain
808 semantic knowledge graph enrichment by integrating data from multiple fields and will be exploited in
809 future developments.

810 **7. Limitations and future directions**

811 Although the proposed process successfully identified most HVAC element connections and contain-
812 ments among the HVAC terminal units and building spaces, it has several limitations, primarily due to
813 the quality of the BIM input data.

814 If surfaces in both boundary representations of the BIM elements of a checked pair are missing or
815 incorrectly oriented—facing inward instead of outward—clash and containment detection for that pair
816 cannot be performed. In such cases, regions of the three-dimensional space cannot be classified as inside
817 or outside any of the elements in the pair. Only pairs in which neither element or only one element has
818 a surface error can be effectively checked for clashes or containments.

819 If BIM elements are attached or intersecting but not actually connected (as shown in part a of
820 Figure 13 and the top right case in Table 1), are mistakenly identified as connected by the proposed
821 methodology. These cases are characterized as False Positive (FP) cases. Similarly, there are instances
822 where MEP components are physically connected in reality, but are not geometrically connected in
823 the as-designed BIM data (as illustrated in parts b and c of Figure 13 and in the bottom left case in
824 Table 1). These cases are classified as False Negative (FN) cases. To correct these inconsistencies, the
825 methodology will be enhanced with a GUI-assisted deletion process in the future, allowing the user to
826 detect, visually verify and address such cases via the use of an appropriate BIM authoring tool.

827 The design errors presented in Figure 13 result in missing or incorrect connections between BIM ele-
828 ments, which cause inaccuracies in the generated HVAC topology graph. These errors can be corrected
829 in future developments, through an iterative process involving visual inspection and verification using
830 a GUI, followed by design corrections and IFC export using a BIM authoring tool. By the end of this
831 process, an error-free BIM MEP file will be produced, enabling the proposed methodology to generate
832 an accurate HVAC topology that is ready for building energy performance simulation.

833 Finally, in some cases, the semantic connections inferred from geometric relation checks between
834 pairs of BIM elements are already present in the BIM data. In these situations, the proposed method-
835 ology can be used as a supplementary tool to validate the accuracy of these pre-existing semantic con-
836 nections. The geometry-induced MEP graphs have the potential to generate a comprehensive HVAC
837 system topology, supporting the automation of building performance simulation models and aiding fault
838 detection and diagnostics during building operations through the development of building digital twins.
839 The knowledge graph, as a digital counterpart that abstracts and represents real-world information,
840 offers designers a more accessible understanding of the MEP systems. This structured representation
841 can further facilitate the identification and correction of errors that might otherwise remain hidden in
842 raw data.

843 In conclusion, the complexity of MEP systems makes the geometric relationships among MEP el-
844 ements insufficient for accurately inferring semantic connections. This work proposes an a posteriori
845 approach, using error detection rules combined with manual intervention, to identify and correct poten-
846 tial issues, thus establishing reliable semantic connections. However, directly inferring precise semantic
847 relations from geometric data alone remains challenging. Future work will focus on refining the error
848 detection ruleset, to enhance the reliability of inferring semantic connections from geometric relation-
849 ships.

850 8. Conclusions

851 The geometric connections within BIM models are crucial for uncovering non-geometric semantic
852 connections among their elements. Leveraging these connections can effectively deduce further semantic
853 relationships among the elements. This dual function not only aids in connecting isolated structures
854 within semantic graphs across different data domains but also enhances the connectivity of existing
855 graphs by introducing additional links between elements.

856 As it was demonstrated, geometric containment relations between IFC space elements from the
857 architecture domain and MEP terminal units from the MEP domain can be used to infer containment
858 relations among these elements, supporting a cross-domain linkage between architecture and MEP.
859 Additionally, intersections or adjacencies between the geometric representations of MEP elements might
860 reveal flow connections between them. The exploitation of this concept has two benefits. On the one
861 hand, the identification of these semantic connections can help in the generation of the HVAC topology
862 of a building and thus facilitate the automatic BIM2BEM generation process. On the other, these
863 geometric relations can reveal design errors involving MEP components, such as clashes between pipe
864 elements. Finally, using semantic reasoning on the detected geometric relationships, missing semantic
865 connections that are related to missing MEP elements can also be identified.

866 To enable these operations, a Geometric Relation Checking (GRC) tool is introduced. GRC detects
867 three types of geometric relations among pairs of geometric representations of BIM elements contained
868 in IFC files that are clash, intersection, and containment. Using these relationships applied to the
869 geometric representations of building space volumes and MEP elements, connectivity relations among
870 MEP elements, as well as containment relations between MEP elements and building spaces, can be
871 inferred. To enable fast execution, GRC is written in C++ using multi-thread libraries to enable parallel
872 runs on multi-core processors achieving millions of pair checks in a minute time scale.

873 It has been shown that the GRC tool can serve as a central element within a process flow that
874 produces a Geometry-induced knowledge graph representing a building’s MEP (Mechanical, Electrical,
875 Plumbing) network using architectural and MEP BIM (Building Information Modeling) input data in
876 the IFC format. The effectiveness of this proposed workflow was demonstrated through its application
877 to the air-loop and water-loop systems of the podium in UCL’s One Pool Street building. The HVAC
878 system of this building showcases complexity and diversity in MEP components, as well as substantial
879 data capacity, providing sufficient evidence of the proposed workflow’s capability in handling large and
880 intricate datasets. As the demand for knowledge graph generation grows to support the digitalization
881 of building stocks, the necessity for workflows like the one introduced will become increasingly evident,
882 potentially expanding its utilization beyond architecture and MEP to other BIM data domains.

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